

Instructional Quality and Faculty Behaviors in Virtual Exchange Programs: A Study of Higher Education Institutions from Philippines and Indonesia

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Article Information

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Abstract:

This study evaluated the effectiveness of a virtual faculty and student exchange program between a higher education institution (HEI) in the Philippines and Indonesia. Data were collected from selected student participants from the higher education institutions from both countries using a descriptive research design. The study found that the program was successful in terms of instructional quality and behaviors of instructors, with respondents viewing the quality of course materials, structure, and delivery as high. The instructors were also observed to exhibit positive and great behaviors, creating a favorable learning environment for their students. Moreover, there were no significant differences in the assessment based on demographic profiles and the evaluation of the quality of course

materials, structure, and delivery, as well as the views on the behaviors of the instructors. These results can serve as a foundation for improving future similar international endeavors using ICT as a medium. The study suggested that ICT can be a promising tool for international exchange programs, providing high-quality education for students from different countries. These findings can aid in the design and implementation of future international endeavors in higher education institutions.

Keywords: *higher education, internationalization, instructional quality assessment, instructors' behavior, virtual faculty and student exchange.*

Introduction

In today's modern world, many web-based learning platforms are available that enable the creation of virtual learning environments and meaningful learning activities (Wihlborg & Friberg, 2016). These platforms can give learners access to various resources, tools, and materials that can assist them in learning and accomplishing their goals.

Online spaces called virtual learning environments simulate traditional classroom environments, enabling learners to engage with

educational content and activities from remote locations (Ng, 2021). These environments can be created using web-based learning platforms like Learning Management Systems (LMS), Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs), and online collaboration tools. Learners can access these virtual environments from anywhere and at any time, provided they have an internet connection, using their computers, laptops, or mobile devices (Bonneau & Cramer, 2021).

Schuell (1986) asserted that the primary responsibility of a teacher was to motivate

students to participate in learning activities that were expected to lead to the desired educational outcomes. It was crucial to note that the student's actions carried more significance than those of the teacher. Meaningful learning activities were designed to help learners engage with the content and acquire knowledge in a way that was relevant, interesting, and applicable to their lives. Web-based learning platforms could create various interactive and engaging activities, such as quizzes, simulations, games, discussions, and multimedia presentations.

In today's modern education landscape, higher education can no longer be viewed solely in a national context (Qiang, 2003). Institutions now see it as a result of their efforts to improve their position within their networks (Schweizer et al., 2010). Internationalization in higher education involves integrating an international, intercultural, or global dimension into the teaching, research, and service functions of universities and colleges. This process is critical in developing global competencies among students, attracting international students from partner institutions abroad, enhancing research, and creating global citizens.

At the onset of the coronavirus pandemic, a higher education institution in the Philippines and in Indonesia underwent a virtual faculty and student exchange program to strengthen collaboration and partnership amidst the pandemic. This academic endeavor was a valuable opportunity to assess the instructional quality and faculty behaviors of both higher education institutions in the virtual faculty and student exchange program, providing a basis for improving the quality of such learning engagements in the future.

Despite the growing interest in virtual faculty and student exchange programs in higher education, there is a research gap regarding the need to conduct a comparative study between higher learning institutions in the Philippines and Indonesia that have undergone such

programs. Specifically, it is necessary to understand the impact of these virtual faculty exchange programs on instructional quality and faculty behaviors in these countries. While literature on the benefits of virtual exchange programs is available, there is limited research that compares the experiences of faculty members in different countries. Therefore, a comparative study between the Philippines and Indonesia would provide valuable insights into the similarities and differences in instructional quality and faculty behaviors resulting from virtual faculty and student exchange programs in these two countries. The findings of this study can inform the development of best practices for virtual exchange programs and guide policy-makers and educational institutions in improving the quality of education in both countries.

Statement of the Problem

The primary objective of this study was to compare and evaluate the instructional quality and behaviors of instructors participating in a virtual faculty and student exchange program between a higher education institution in the Philippines and Indonesia.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following:

1. How may the demographic profile of the respondents be described in terms of
 - 1.1. Sex; and
 - 1.2. Country of Origin?
2. How may the assessment on the quality of instructions received by the respondents be described?
3. How may the assessment on the behavior of the instructors in the virtual faculty and students exchange program be described?
4. Is there a significant difference between the demographic profiles of the respondents and their view on the quality of instructions received?
5. Is there a significant difference between the demographic profiles of the respondents and their assessment on the behavior of the instructors during the virtual faculty and student exchange program?

- What plan of action may be suggested based from the results of the assessment in the virtual faculty and student exchange program?

Materials and Methods

A descriptive research design is a type of research methodology that involves collecting data in order to describe and analyze the characteristics, behaviors, or attitudes of a particular group or phenomenon. Descriptive research is used when the primary objective is to describe something, rather than to test a specific hypothesis or determine causality (McCombes, 2022).

In this study, a descriptive research design was used, and data was collected through a survey method. The survey questionnaire was based on the study conducted by Olipas et al. (2022). The respondents of the study were the participants of the faculty and student exchange program in an HEI in the Philippines and Indonesia. Since the data gathering happened during the second semester of Academic Year 2021-2022, which was during the peak of the pandemic, Google Forms were utilized. It was expressed in the form that the participation was purely voluntary. The researcher sought informed consent from the respondents. The needed information was included in the electronic instrument. Additionally, the researcher ensured that the data collected were only used for the purpose of this study and were taken care of with the utmost confidentiality.

When the data were collected, they were then analyzed and summarized to provide a clear picture of the instructional quality and faculty behaviors in the virtual faculty and student exchange program in higher education in the Philippines and Indonesia. Table 1 presented the scoring guide used in this study.

Table 1. Scoring Guide

Numerical Rating	Range	Level of Quality of Course Materials, Structure, and Delivery	Level of Frequency-Based Behavior
4	3.26 – 4.00	High Quality	Always
3	2.51 – 3.25	Moderate Quality	Often
2	1.76 – 2.50	Low Quality	Seldom
1	1.00 – 1.75	No Quality	Never

Results and Discussion

Demographic Profile of the Respondents

The following sections present the demographic profile of the respondents to provide valuable insights into the distribution of the respondents in terms of sex and country of origin.

Sex of the Respondents

Figure 1 presents the percentage distribution in terms of the sex of the respondents.

Figure 1. Percentage Distribution based on Sex

Presenting the distribution based on sex is essential to understand sex representation in the study. Furthermore, it can contribute to a deeper analysis to support the data presented in the succeeding tables.

Country of Participating Students in the Virtual Faculty and Student Exchange Program

Figure 2 shows the percentage distribution of respondents based on their countries of origin. Describing this distribution is important for gaining a better understanding of how the program participants were distributed across different nations.

Figure 2. Percentage Distribution based on country of participating students in the program

Assessment on the Quality of Course Materials, Structure and Delivery

Table 2 presents the results of the assessment made by the respondents on the quality of course materials, structure, and delivery used during the virtual program.

Table 2. Quality of Course Materials, Structure and Delivery

Item Statements	Mean Rating	Verbal Interpretation
My learning was greatly enhanced by the online/threaded discussions (such as Google Classroom, Zoom, and Google Meet).	3.62	High Quality
Appropriate learning materials necessary for online learning were	3.71	High Quality

utilized to conduct and deliver the activities.		
The topics covered in the course are arranged in a logical and consistent manner.	3.62	High Quality
The lessons in the course are intellectually stimulating.	3.56	High Quality
The provided course materials enhance my learning.	3.67	High Quality
Grand Mean	3.64	
Verbal Interpretation	High Quality	

Assessment on the Behavior of Instructors

In Table 3 the result of the assessment on the view of the respondents about the behavior of the instructors is presented.

Table 3. Behaviors of Instructors

Item Statements	Mean Rating	Verbal Interpretation
The instructor/professor shows respect towards the students.	3.94	Always
Requests or inquiries were promptly addressed by the instructors/professors.	3.79	Always
Timely feedback was given to me by the instructor/professor.	3.81	Always
The instructor/professor gave me chances to learn from my peers.	3.85	Always
Grand Mean	3.85	
Verbal Interpretation	Always	

Significant Difference on the Assessment on the Quality of Materials, Structure and Delivery (Respondents are grouped based on Demographic Profiles)

Table 4 shows the result of the analysis on the significant difference between the quality of materials, structure, and delivery, and the demographic variables of the respondents.

Table 4. Correlation Analysis between Profile and Quality of Materials, Structure and Delivery

Variables	Quality of Materials, Structure and Delivery	Decision
Sex	0.722	Not Significant
Country of Origin	0.339	Not Significant

Significant Difference on the Assessment on the Behaviors of the Instructors/Professors when Respondents are grouped based on Demographic Profiles

The results of the analysis testing the difference in instructor behavior based on the demographic profiles of the respondents are presented in Table 5.

Table 5. Correlation Analysis between Profile and Behavior of the Instructors

Variables	Behavior of the Instructors	Decision
Sex	0.516	Not Significant
Country of Origin	0.051	Not Significant

Discussion

When looking at Figure 1, it is apparent that male respondents have a larger percentage of distribution at 69.2% compared to women who only make up 30.8%. A notable difference of 38.4% exists between the sexes of the respondents. Understanding the percentage distribution between male and female respondents provides valuable insights into the gender representation of the sample. This information is significant in evaluating whether the sample is representative of the general population or a specific sub-group of interest.

Based on the data, it can be noted that there was a larger number of male participants in the virtual faculty and student exchange program. However, this does not indicate that female students are incapable of participating in such activities. Typically, computing courses, like information technology, are mostly dominated by males. Thus, the results support the existing

trend based on the disparity that exists between the number of males and females enrolled in computing courses (Commission on Higher Education, 2022; Olipas, 2023).

Higher Education Institutions should pursue programs and activities that can intensify the recruitment of female students in computing programs to lessen the gender gap. Furthermore, women should be encouraged to venture into computing programs to become more empowered in the 21st century and to contribute to the realization of solutions for the United Nations Sustainable Development. Goal No. 5 to “achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls” (Goal 5 | Department of Economic and Social Affairs, n.d.).

Figure 2 shows that 67.3% of the participants came from an HEI in the Philippines, while 32.7% came from an HEI in Indonesia, resulting in a 34.6% difference in distribution. This unequal distribution, though potentially introducing biases and limitations, can also be interpreted positively. Firstly, it indicates the success of the study in recruiting a large and diverse pool of participants from the Philippines, reflecting the country's interest and commitment to global academic exchanges. Secondly, it highlights the unique challenges and opportunities faced by each country in promoting quality virtual academic programs, as reflected in the different experiences and perspectives of the participants. Such a finding emphasizes the need for tailored interventions to support the growth and sustainability of virtual academic programs in both countries and beyond.

Assessing the quality of course materials, structure, and delivery of instruction in the virtual faculty and student exchange program is crucial for several reasons. Firstly, the quality of these elements directly affects the effectiveness of the program in achieving its intended learning outcomes. Poorly designed course materials, ineffective structure, and delivery of instruction can result in students failing to learn the required knowledge and skills.

Secondly, assessing the quality of course materials, structure, and delivery of instruction helps to identify areas that need improvement. By understanding the strengths and weaknesses of the program, instructors and administrators can make informed decisions about changes that can enhance the program's effectiveness.

Thirdly, assessing the quality of course materials, structure, and delivery of instruction ensures that the program is aligned with the institution's academic standards and policies. Virtual faculty and student exchange programs need to meet the same standards as traditional programs to ensure that the degrees and credits earned are recognized and respected by other institutions and employers.

Lastly, assessing the quality of course materials, structure, and delivery of instruction helps to ensure that the program is inclusive and accessible to all students, regardless of their background and abilities. Instructors and administrators can use the assessment results to identify and address any barriers to learning that students may face, such as language, technology, or cultural barriers.

In Table 2, it can be observed that the respondents generally viewed the course materials, structure, and delivery in the virtual faculty and students exchange program with high quality as reflected in the overall computed mean rating 3.64. The students highly appreciated the use of online/threaded discussions such as Google Classroom, Zoom, and Google Meet as it greatly enhanced their learning experience with an average rating of 3.62. The utilization of appropriate learning materials for online learning was also highly appreciated by the students, with an average rating of 3.71.

Furthermore, the students found the arrangement of topics in the course to be logical and consistent with an average rating of 3.62. However, the intellectual stimulation of the lessons received a slightly lower average rating of

3.56, indicating that there may be some areas for improvement in this aspect. Nonetheless, the provided course materials were still perceived to enhance their learning with an average rating of 3.67.

In summary for Table 2, the results suggest that the use of online/threaded discussions and appropriate learning materials are effective in enhancing the students' learning experience, and the logical arrangement of topics and provided course materials can further contribute to their learning.

Assessing the behaviors of the instructors involved in the faculty and student exchange program is important for several reasons. Firstly, instructors play a critical role in the success of the program. They are responsible for designing and delivering the course materials, providing feedback and support to students, and facilitating discussions and interactions among participants. Assessing their behaviors helps to ensure that they are effectively fulfilling these responsibilities and contributing to the program's success.

Secondly, assessing the behaviors of the instructors helps to identify areas that need improvement. Instructors may have different levels of experience and expertise in virtual teaching and may require support and training to effectively deliver the course materials and interact with students in a virtual environment. Identifying these areas of improvement can help to enhance the effectiveness of the program and ensure that students are receiving high-quality instruction.

Thirdly, assessing the behaviors of the instructors helps to ensure that they are adhering to the institution's academic standards and policies. Instructors need to meet the same standards as those teaching in traditional programs to ensure that the program's degrees and credits earned are recognized and respected by other institutions and employers.

Lastly, assessing the behaviors of the instructors helps to ensure that the program is inclusive and accessible to all students, regardless of their background and abilities. Instructors need to create an inclusive and supportive learning environment that accommodates the needs of diverse learners. Assessing their behaviors can help to identify any barriers to learning that students may face and ensure that they are addressed appropriately.

As presented in Table 3, the respondents generally expressed that they have always observed good behaviors of the instructors involved in the program as reflected in the overall mean rating of 3.85.

Specifically, the students reported a high level of respect shown towards them by their instructors/professors, with an average rating of 3.94, which indicates that the instructors/professors were able to create a positive learning environment for the students. The prompt addressing of requests or inquiries by the instructors/professors was also highly rated by the students, with an average rating of 3.79. This indicates that the instructors/professors were able to respond to the students' needs and provide support promptly. The provision of timely feedback was also perceived positively by the students, with an average rating of 3.81. This suggests that the instructors/professors were able to give constructive feedback to the students in a timely manner, which can help to improve their learning outcomes. The students also reported having opportunities to learn from their peers, with an average rating of 3.85. This indicates that the instructors/professors encouraged collaboration and teamwork among the students, which can help to foster a positive learning environment and enhance the students' learning outcomes.

In summary for Table 3, the data suggest that the instructors/professors involved in the faculty and student exchange program exhibited

positive behaviors towards the students, which can contribute to the effectiveness of the program in achieving its intended learning outcomes.

Table 4 analyzed the impact of two variables, "Sex" and "Country of Origin," on the "Quality of Materials, Structure, and Delivery" of the virtual faculty and student exchange program. The obtained p-values for these variables were 0.722 and 0.339, respectively. These values indicate that differences in the ratings of the program's quality based on sex or country of origin were not statistically significant.

This finding suggests that the program's quality was perceived to be consistent regardless of the students' sex or country of origin. However, it's important to note that non-significance doesn't necessarily imply the absence of differences. Other factors, such as the instructor's behavior or course content, could still affect the perceived quality of the program.

Therefore, while the study suggests that sex and country of origin might not be crucial factors, it's still essential to consider other aspects that could potentially impact the perceived quality of the program. This could include addressing individual learning styles and preferences and tailoring the program accordingly.

Table 5 shows the results of an analysis that aimed to determine the impact of two variables, "Sex" and "Country of Origin," on the "Behavior of the Instructors/Professors" in a faculty and student exchange program. The reported p-values for sex and country of origin were 0.516 and 0.051, respectively.

The non-significant p-values suggest that there is no evidence of a meaningful relationship between sex or country of origin and the behavior of the instructors/professors in the program. This means that the behavior of the instructors/professors was perceived to be consistent regardless of the student's sex or country of origin.

However, it is important to note that the lack of statistical significance does not necessarily mean that there is no real-world difference between groups. It only suggests that any observed differences may have occurred by chance and may not be reliably replicated in other samples or populations. Therefore, while the results suggest that sex and country of origin may not be important factors in the behavior of instructors/professors, it is still important to consider other factors that may influence the behavior of instructors/professors, such as their training, teaching styles, and cultural backgrounds.

Based on the positive results of the assessment in the virtual faculty and student exchange program, some possible plans of action that can be suggested are:

1. Expanding and promoting the virtual exchange program to other higher education institutions in different countries to provide more opportunities for students to gain international exposure and education.
2. Providing training and resources for instructors to further enhance their skills in creating a favorable learning environment and delivering high-quality course materials through ICT.
3. Conducting regular assessments and evaluations to monitor the program's effectiveness and identify areas for improvement.
4. Encouraging more student and faculty participation in the program by offering incentives such as scholarships, grants, or academic credit.
5. Establishing partnerships with industry and government organizations to provide more opportunities for students to gain practical experience and apply their knowledge in real-world settings.

Conclusion

Based on the objectives of the study, the findings show that the virtual faculty and student exchange program between the higher education institution in the Philippines and Indonesia was successful in terms of instructional quality and behaviors of instructors. A descriptive research design was used, and the selected student participants from the Philippines and Indonesia provided data for the study. The study found that more males participated in the study, and more participants came from the Philippines.

Regarding the quality of course materials, structure, and delivery, respondents expressed that they view it with high quality, indicating the effectiveness of the virtual exchange program. Moreover, a positive and great behaviors of instructors were always observed, which showed that the instructors were able to create a favorable learning environment for their students.

The study also found no significant difference in the assessment made based on the demographic profiles and the assessment on the quality of course materials, structure, and delivery, as well as the views on the behaviors of the instructors. These results can be a basis for improving future similar international endeavors made by each higher education institution with respect to the use of ICT as a medium.

In conclusion, the virtual faculty and student exchange program between the higher education institution in the Philippines and Indonesia proved to be successful in terms of instructional quality and behaviors of instructors. The positive results suggest that the use of ICT as a medium for international exchange programs can be a promising tool in providing high-quality education for students from different countries. These findings can help improve the design and implementation of future similar international endeavors in higher education institutions.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions drawn from the study, the following recommendations can be made:

1. Higher education institutions should continue to explore the use of ICT as a medium for international exchange programs. The positive results of this study demonstrate that it can be an effective tool in providing high-quality education for students from different countries.
2. Instructors participating in virtual exchange programs should be trained and equipped with the necessary skills to effectively facilitate online learning. This includes the ability to create a favorable learning environment and deliver high-quality course materials.
3. The study found no significant difference in the assessment based on demographic profiles, indicating that the virtual exchange program can be an inclusive platform for students from diverse backgrounds. However, further research can explore the experiences of minority groups to ensure that they are not left behind in the virtual exchange program.
4. Lastly, continuous monitoring and evaluation of the virtual exchange program should be conducted to ensure that it remains effective in achieving its objectives. The findings of this study can serve as a foundation for the design and implementation of future international endeavors in higher education institutions.

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Conflict of interests

The researcher declares no conflict of interest.

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